

Sequential Analysis of Problems Encountered by Students in Accomplishing Performance Tasks

Glen R. Mangali¹, Jesus M. Cababa², Nenita A. Pascual², Leah M. Donasco²,
Elvira M. Tabinas²

¹College of Liberal Arts and Sciences, Colegio De San Juan De Letran Manila

²Basic Education Department, Colegio De San Juan De Letran Manila

Email address: glen.mangali@lettran.edu.ph

Abstract— *Performance Task is proven to improve the teaching and learning processes. This study intend to find out the problems that grade 8 students encounter in accomplishing performance tasks in relation to the teacher, assessment, classroom management, learning environment, classroom technology and others. The findings showed that specific problems pertaining to the teacher, assessment, learning environment or venue, classroom management, and classroom materials are encountered by students which affected the accomplishment of performance tasks.. Among these problems, the learning environment or venue is the greatest predictor followed by classroom management, assessment, classroom materials and teacher.*

From the findings, the study has the following implications. First, appropriate measures must be undertaken to address the problems that are attributable to the teacher, assessment, learning environment or venue, classroom management, classroom materials, deadline of submission, students' emotional and personal state, simultaneous performance tasks, teacher's subjectivity and grouping of students in future performance tasks. Second, any initiative of improvement must prioritize the aspect of learning environment or venue followed by classroom management, assessment, classroom materials and teachers. Lastly, the study can contribute in education and research as a source of data for future similar researches.

Keywords— *Performance Tasks, Assessment, Teaching and Learning.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Performance tasks are given as authentic assessment because they help teachers improve the teaching and learning processes (Shalev, 2018). They are authentic assessment tools that measure higher-order thinking skills and data-driven instruction which optimize learning (Abbot & Wren, 2016). Performance tasks present students with real situations unlike the common self-contained academic exercises (Chun, 2012) and in contrast with traditional paper and pencil tests that measure mastery, they are engaging and worthwhile (Roche & Cheeseman, 2013). According to Mehrens (1992), a performance task distinguishes a student's ability from his or her ideas. Linn & Gronlund (2000) emphasize that more than the knowledge, a performance task focuses on creating something, the procedure of doing, and the end product.

Requirement of performance tasks in the high school level of Letran basic education is a major learning activity. Each subject requires every student to accomplish a task whether collaboratively or individually. Its purpose to develop creativity and attain mastery are reflected by the relevant

outcomes that they submit. If done properly and accomplished on time, these outputs are good indicators of authentic learning.

Doing performance tasks allows students to think independently and deviate from teacher inquiry (Shepard, 1991). This form of assessment is authentic with realistic daily life applications (Spady, & Marshall, 1991). Examples of performance tasks include writing a report, designing a presentation and doing demonstration (Nitko, 2004), story writing, sketching or diagramming (Airasian, 2000; McMillan, 2007), and scientific outputs (Çepni, 2005). Skills like writing personal life experiences (Airasian, 2001; Birgin, 2003; Metin, 2008; Metin & Birişçi, 2010), inquiry (Metin, 2008), presentation (Airasian, 2001), problem solving (Kim, 2005), science processes (Airasian, 2001; Çepni, 2005) and high level thinking (Bransford, 1979; Çepni, Logan, 1996) are developed in the process of accomplishing the tasks. Throughout the years that performance tasks have been given as one form of assessment, students were observed to be more creative, independent, and motivated to interact among themselves and with the teacher (Çepni, 2007). It also allowed the teacher to correct misunderstanding, misconception and confusion because of its effectiveness in teaching the concepts (Çepni, 2005; Metin, 2008). Mastery of learning manifests in students' desire to learn more and acquire worthwhile skills with deep understanding through successful performance tasks.

Unaccomplished performance tasks on the other hand are not indicative of deep mastery because of their irrelevance to learning. An unaccomplished performance task is an indication of an unsuccessful performance due to its non-conformity to the assessment tool while its incompleteness is a proof that deep understanding of the subject matter was not attained. Unaccomplished performance tasks impede the progression of the lesson, disallows the teacher to measure real understanding, and deprive the student the chance to develop true understanding and creativity. Teaching and learning suffer when a student fails to accomplish a performance task because it leaves a teacher with no accurate measure of the level of understanding. It has been observed that a number of students fail to accomplish the required performance tasks because of unidentified problems. Primarily, teachers are sources of problems when they fail to identify applicable topics relative to students' degree of

understanding and explain the correct criteria due to poor knowledge in preparing rubrics (Schendel, 2017). Additionally, limited classroom space, lack of time for assessment, below standard learning environment and insufficient technological opportunity (Abbott, 2016) are contributors that hinder a student's compliance to the task. The success of every performance task is dependent on how the characteristics of each factor manifest in the entirety of work.

When performance tasks were introduced, teachers were limited to the use of portfolios and projects with little use to other forms of tasks. Teachers identify insufficient time and the difficulty of these assessments as two factors that obstruct the applicability of performance tasks (Linn, 2000). Teachers' limitation to time and difficulty in preparation greatly manifest in their inability to come up with well-prepared performance tasks. The success of performance tasks is dependent on the teachers who understand the goals of assessment (Airasian, 1994). They must be able to use assessment correctly through an extensive explanation of the learning objectives and the description of the activities to ensure student understanding of these objectives. (Sheppard, 1996). A study by Khattri, Reeve, Kane, and Adamson (1996) found out that teachers who are able to thoroughly explain the learning objectives produce proficient student.

Assessment verifies student learning in order to determine the extent of achievement of curriculum objectives (Bintz, 1991). According to Anderson (1998), adopting the more authentic assessment which are performance based requires time. However, authentic assessment and evaluation activities have become the accepted form (Bay, 2010). Performance task is not only an effective evaluation that can measure progress of the students but the process of accomplishing the task as well (Bullens, 2002). Bahar, Nartgün, Durmuş, and Bıçak (2006) agree to the authenticity of this assessment because it interrelates with real life. Additionally, Turgut and Baykul (2012) stress that the level of accomplishment can be measured by gauging student outputs which enable them to learn concepts and abstract scenarios.

The most appropriate assessment tool in rating a performance task is the rubric. A standard procedure must be followed in designing a rubric. At the start, samples must be selected that will show the different levels of quality so that students may be allowed to examine models representing different performance levels. Students then will identify the criteria for successful performance. With the final criteria, rubric may then be drafted allowing revisions after feedback have been gathered. The teacher then demonstrates how the rubric is used to assess a work sample so that students will be able to use the rubric correctly and assess the performance task as objectively as they can.

Good classroom discipline determines student success in accomplishing tasks because it allows full attention and engagement. Disruption in the classroom redirects the focus of the teacher and the class away from the lesson or activity and is a predictor of failure (McCloughlin C. 2015). Dealing with disruptive behavior accordingly is one of the most challenging tasks of being a teacher (Fidler, 2002). Furthermore, disruptive

students end up as academically deficient (Nelson J., 2004) and receive less instruction (Sutherland, 2008). Classroom discipline which dictates both appropriate and non-disruptive classroom behavior must be managed before learning takes place and full attention to the learning task is attained. Good classroom discipline can be enhanced using the principles of monitoring, modelling, cueing, environmental control and low profile intervention (Daniel, 1986). The monitoring principle constantly checks a student performance and behavior while the modelling principle indicates that students' behavior could be influenced by teachers as role-models. Environmental control necessitates teacher to provide a productive learning environment through manipulations of classroom assets and materials for a task to be successful.

A performance task must simulate a natural environment that must connect a learner with the real-world because authentic learning is a social interaction (Melarney 2000). As such, a learning environment is necessary where students are able to freely interact among themselves with unlimited exchange of ideas. It must be stimulating, engaging and free of distractions. It must provide areas for personal space in order for an individual to think independently and contribute productively to the learning objectives (Visser, 2001). As most student engagements is an almost free for all affair in the exchange of thoughts, a chaotic environment ensues that oftentimes result to confusion or forms of misbehavior. A teacher must ensure that a good learning environment is available before every performance task commences for effective facilitation of the activity. To achieve this, pathways between students and high mobility areas must be unobstructed, student seating arrangement must be free of distractions, and a conducive learning environment with proper ventilation and sufficient lighting must be provided (Visser, 2001).

Every school prioritizes the integration of technology to curriculum because it effectively supplements classroom instruction (Cubin, L., Kirkpatrick, H., & Peck, C. 2001). Technology in education such as media, models, visuals, audio, video and digital media (Wartella, E.A., & Jennings, N. 2000) can motivate students when integrated to the curriculum. Furthermore, it contributes to the improvement of the overall learning venue that promotes student interaction (Lengel, 2006). Daily life activities without access to technology is difficult to think (Williams, 2009). In this age, basic skills in operating a computer and its accessories, browsing the web, or using different applications are necessary (Lewis, 2009). Problems associated with technology in learning include no access to technology and support services, technological illiteracy, absence of interaction, and undesired academic skills (Stine 2004). Skillful students with no access the technology will probably fail. A home with no technological access is an unproductive place even for a creative student. School related deficiencies limit the amount of time to accomplish a specific academic task (Tinto, 2008), more so when computer laboratories and libraries are closed on weekends. Technical problems that students cannot troubleshoot delay work that lead to frustration and loss of motivation and Nash (2005) states that providing students with

technical support reduces frustration. According to Young and Norgard (2006), student success in technology-based activities is dependent on the availability of technical support.

The above discussion formed the basis from which the study was anchored. The study wanted to find out the problems that grade 8 students encounter in accomplishing performance tasks in relation to the teacher, assessment, classroom management, learning environment, classroom technology and others. Additionally, it sought to establish the predictors of a successful performance task relative to the identified variables.

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework shows the flow of the study. The problems that are encountered by grade 8 students in accomplishing performance tasks point to factors namely the subject teacher, the assessment procedure, the classroom management employed by the learning environment, the technology used in accomplishing the tasks and other factors. Each of the factors has no direct effect to the other but individually is a determiner to an accomplished performance tasks as shown by pointed arrows.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section includes the research design, the sample and the research instruments that were used in the conduct of the study. The sources of data, methods and procedure of data gathering and statistical treatment of data are also part of the discussion.

The study used the sequential mixed-method design. The quantitative part of the study was analyzed using the One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to test the mean within the factors and between subjects. Thematic analysis was performed to analyze the responses of the students in the focus group discussion.

Two sections consisting of 77 Grade 8 students of Colegio de San Juan de Letran Basic Education Department served as respondents in the quantitative part of the study. 16 students were selected in the qualitative part. And a five –point Likert scale consisting of 20-item statements was pilot-tested and used.

Data Gathering

The study used a sequential method to analyze the problems encountered by grade 8 students in accomplishing performance tasks. For the quantitative data, the respondents were administered a researcher made, 20 –item questionnaire which was formatted using the excel 2010 software. The questionnaire was installed in the 43 computer units of the basic education computer laboratory 1. The responses were retrieved as an excel worksheet. For the qualitative data, direct responses from the questions from the focus group discussion were gathered and referenced from the audio and video recording of respondents. The detailed responses were transcribed.

Data Analysis

Interval data of the responses from the questionnaire were analyzed using the t-test for two independent samples with unequal variances to determine how one group responded in relation to the other given the independence of each group. At 95%confidence level, degree of freedom of 75, critical value of 1.96, the mean responses of the groups were tested. The second test is the One –Way ANOVA for more than two means to determine whether the differences in the mean responses were significant or not in the five variables at 95%confidence level. The mean response according to the least average to the highest presented the variables as predictors that will most likely hinder a student to accomplish a successful performance tasks.

The transcribed data of the audio and video recording from the focus group discussion were analyzed using the deductive approach. The direct responses were translated to English by a proponent who is an expert in the Filipino language, coded, filtered and synthesized. The synthesis formed the basis of discussion.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The t- test for two independent samples with unequal variances was employed. At 95%confidence level, degree of freedom of 75, critical value of 1.96, the mean responses of the two groups were tested. All values fall within the acceptance region indicating no significant difference in all the mean responses pertaining to the variable that affects the accomplishment of performance tasks in all subjects. With the result, the researchers have concluded that similar conditions in the accomplishment of performance tasks prevail in two independent groups. The groups were then unified as one population.

Table 1 shows the mean responses of seventy- seven (77) grade 8 students pertaining to each item of the five variables that affect the accomplishment of performance tasks in all subjects. With a range of values from the least at 2.86 (CL item number 18) to the highest at 3.91(Math item number 3), it shows that the mean responses range from neutral (2.5-3.4) to agree (3.5-4.4).

Table 1 Mean Responses of Students on Five Variables that Affect the Accomplishment of Performance Tasks Across Subjects

	Math	Arabic	TLE	English	Science	CL	MARAH	Finance
I. The Teacher :	3.70	3.50	3.64	3.51	3.49	3.03	3.67	3.62
1. The teacher provides accurate description of the task with ideal samples.	3.83	3.51	3.65	3.66	3.44	2.92	3.75	3.69
2. The teacher motivates each student to develop creativity.	3.38	3.42	3.71	3.35	3.44	2.97	3.68	3.74
3. The teacher provides clear learning goals.	3.91	3.51	3.60	3.56	3.49	3.16	3.78	3.49
4. The teacher provides well-planned tasks.	3.69	3.57	3.58	3.45	3.57	3.08	3.47	3.55
II. The Assessment:	3.43	3.47	3.43	3.49	3.42	3.06	3.58	3.55
5. The method used in grading the output promotes quality of work.	3.57	3.51	3.51	3.42	3.27	3.08	3.73	3.70
6. The method used in grading the output is fair.	3.31	3.44	3.25	3.45	3.42	2.97	3.62	3.42
7. The method used in grading the output has identified criteria.	3.56	3.48	3.56	3.51	3.49	3.06	3.61	3.48
8. The method used in grading the output has clear objectives .	3.27	3.45	3.42	3.57	3.49	3.12	3.36	3.60
III. The Classroom Management	3.43	3.63	3.29	3.50	3.48	3.11	3.49	3.40
9. The control of the classroom allows immediate attention to students' concern.	3.44	3.55	3.23	3.39	3.42	2.97	3.52	3.38
10. The control of the classroom ensures discipline throughout the activity.	3.30	3.70	3.03	3.49	3.48	3.09	3.45	3.39
11. The control of the classroom allows consistent monitoring of the activity.	3.65	3.70	3.56	3.56	3.58	3.22	3.47	3.43
IV. The Learning Environment	3.29	3.33	3.45	3.52	3.40	3.14	3.55	3.51
12. The place of activity has good arrangement to enhance successful output.	3.12	3.30	3.47	3.51	3.42	3.10	3.44	3.56
13. The place of activity has sufficient space for students to move freely.	3.45	3.25	3.39	3.43	3.40	3.23	3.61	3.48
14. The place of activity provides student arrangements to limit distractions.	3.19	3.39	3.40	3.52	3.35	3.10	3.58	3.53
15. The place of activity provides space for either individual or group activity.	3.38	3.39	3.55	3.62	3.42	3.13	3.56	3.45
V. The Classroom Technology:	3.42	3.38	3.57	3.55	3.60	3.10	3.57	3.37
16. The classroom equipment or materials provide opportunity to develop technical or real-life skills.	3.39	3.27	3.45	3.55	3.57	3.18	3.66	3.35
17. The classroom equipment or materials have available assistance to ensure uninterrupted use.	3.27	3.40	3.73	3.70	3.52	2.86	3.55	3.32
18. The classroom equipment or materials are available.	3.49	3.31	3.48	3.49	3.75	3.13	3.70	3.39
19. The classroom equipment or materials develop interactive skills.	3.34	3.48	3.55	3.64	3.40	3.05	3.51	3.40
20. The classroom equipment or materials supplement learning skills.	3.58	3.43	3.64	3.27	3.70	3.27	3.38	3.38

Table 2. One –Way ANOVA for the Effects of Teacher in Accomplishing Performance Tasks in Grade 8

ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	Df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	1.269	7	0.181	11.24	3E-06	2.42
Within Groups	0.387	24	0.016			
Total	1.656	31				

Table 2 shows the F value of the mean responses of students on the effects of teacher in accomplishing performance tasks. The F value is 11.24 which is greater than the critical value of 2.43. This signifies that the mean responses pertaining to the effects of teachers is significantly different among the 8 subjects. Students had *neutral* responses that the teacher: 1). provides accurate description of the task with ideal samples 2). motivates each student to develop creativity 3). provides clear learning goals and 4). provides well-planned tasks. The result had revealed that different teachers had varying effects with the students and their performance tasks.

Table 3. One –Way ANOVA for the Effects of Assessment in Accomplishing Performance Tasks in Grade 8

ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	Df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.72	7	0.103	7.96	5E-05	2.42
Within Groups	0.31	24	0.013			
Total	1.03	31				

Table 3 shows the F value of the mean responses of students on the effects of assessment in accomplishing performance tasks. The F value of 7.96 is greater than critical value of 2.42 which indicates that the mean responses pertaining to the effects of assessment is significantly different among the 8 subjects. Students had *neutral* responses that 1). the method used in grading the output promotes quality of work, 2). The assessment is fair, has clear objectives and 3). identified criteria. The result had revealed that different forms of assessments had varying effects with the students and their performance tasks.

Table 4. One –Way ANOVA for the Effects of Classroom Management in Accomplishing Performance Task in Grade 8

ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	Df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.584	7	0.083	4.67	0.005	2.66
Within Groups	0.286	16	0.018			
Total	0.87	23				

Table 4 shows the F value of the mean responses of students on the effects of classroom management in accomplishing performance tasks. The F value of 4.67 is greater than the critical value of 2.66 which means that the mean responses pertaining to the effects of a managed class is significantly different among the 8 subjects. Students had *neutral* responses that 1). a managed classroom allows immediate attention to students' concern and 2). ensures discipline throughout the activity. However, they agreed that the control of the classroom allows consistent monitoring of the activity. The result had revealed that different ways of managing a classroom management had varying effects with the students and their performance tasks.

Table 5. One –Way ANOVA for the Effects of Learning Environment in Accomplishing Performance Tasks in Grade 8

ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	Df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.537	7	0.077	11.45	3E-06	2.423
Within Groups	0.161	24	0.007			
Total	0.698	31				

Table 5 shows the F value of the mean responses of students on the effects of learning environment in accomplishing performance tasks. The F value of 11.45, greater than the critical value of 2.43 which means that the mean responses pertaining to the effects of a managed class is significantly different among the 8 subjects. Students had *neutral* responses that 1). a managed classroom allows immediate attention to students' concern and 2). ensures discipline throughout the activity. However, they agreed that the control of the classroom allows consistent monitoring of the activity. The result had revealed that different learning environments had varying effects with the students and their performance tasks.

Table 6. One –Way ANOVA for the Effects of Classroom Technology in Accomplishing Performance Tasks in Grade 8

ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	Df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.977	7	0.14	9.74	2E-06	2.3
Within Groups	0.459	32	0.014			
Total	1.436	39				

Table 6 shows the F value of the mean responses of students on the effects of classroom technology in accomplishing performance tasks. The F value of 9.74 is greater than the critical value of 2.3 which signifies that the mean responses are significantly different among the 8 subjects. Students had neutral responses that the classroom equipment or materials 1). provide opportunity to develop technical or real-life skills, 2). have available assistance to ensure uninterrupted use, 3). are available, 4). develop interactive skills, and 5). supplement learning skills. The result had revealed that the applications of different classroom technology had varying effects with the students and their performance tasks.

Table 7. Ranking of Variables Based on Average of Mean Responses in Accomplishing Performance Tasks in Grade 8

Factors in Accomplishing Performance Tasks	Math	Aralin	TLE	English	Science	CL	MARPEH	Filipino	Average	Rating
The Learning Environment	3.29	3.33	3.45	3.52	3.40	3.14	3.55	3.51	3.40	Neutral
The Classroom Management	3.43	3.63	3.29	3.50	3.48	3.11	3.49	3.40	3.42	Neutral
The Assessment	3.43	3.47	3.43	3.49	3.42	3.06	3.58	3.55	3.43	Neutral
The Classroom Technology	3.42	3.38	3.57	3.55	3.60	3.10	3.57	3.37	3.44	Neutral
The Teacher	3.70	3.50	3.64	3.51	3.49	3.03	3.67	3.62	3.52	Agree

Table 7 shows the average of the mean responses of grade 8 students pertaining to the five (5) variables that affect the accomplishment of performance tasks in their subjects. The average mean responses are ranked from the smallest average to the biggest to present the variables as predictors that will most likely hinder a student to accomplish a successful performance tasks. In order from the greatest predictor to the least are the learning environment (M= 3.40), classroom management (M=3.42), assessment (M=3.43), classroom technology (M=3.44) and teacher (M=3.52). The ranking shows that the learning environment is the greatest predictor of an unaccomplished performance task.

Fig. 2. The Triple P Diagram

The Triple P is an acronym for the PeTa relative to Problems that Predict. The Triple P diagram visualizes the concept of accomplished and unaccomplished performance tasks that are both dependent to the problems related to the learning environment or venue, classroom management, assessment, classroom materials and teachers, arranged in particular order to indicate how they predict failure. In this diagram, five candles with the same intensities and arranged from top to bottom represent the five sources of problems that predictably affect a successful performance task. When all these factors are appropriately addressed before or during the accomplishment of any task, these candles are lighted and collectively emit a bright light that is able to clearly illumine objects. Similar to the bright light is an accomplished performance task that positively affects (illuminated circles) a student because it reflects the desired objective of the task and leaves a remarkable impact. It improves understanding and motivation, reflects learning, brings joy, develops creativity, promotes cooperation, hard work, and positive attitude towards the task through a sense of accomplishment. On the other hand, when any of these problems is not addressed, a candle loses intensity and brightness turn to dimness. Dimness is the unaccomplished performance task with implicit negative effects (dim circles) such as poor mastery, poor understanding, lack of creativity and poor performance.

Qualitative data from the direct responses in the focus group discussion were analyzed to contextualize the quantitative findings and give it a more detailed examination.

Problems

This theme encapsulates the problems that students encounter in accomplishing performance tasks. Specific problems with the teachers were identified from the direct responses.

“.. halimbawa kunwari sa English, gagawa ka na ng poem , pwede i-improve, at pagpatong patungan, pwedeng gumawa ka na ng draft, kunwari sa science gagawa ka ng bottle na rocket, me posibilidad na na di gumana or sumablay... “Student 6 ,”...so kung sumablay pwedeng mawalan ng gana or mawalan ng motivation gumawa, possible na ayaw na nila gawin or bumaba na ang grade nila... parang nawawalan po sila ng students ng motivation po na gumawa ng PT kasi dahil baka mababa yung binibigay na score, ganun, nakaka- apekto talaga..”

“..teachers create problems when subject teachers assign different tasks and levels of difficulty, ...failure leads low grades ,loss of interest, and motivation”

“..parang sa iba po kahit po na inexplain ng teacher yung ibang students din po di din po nakikinig then paulit ulit lang o then wala na din po, nawala na yung instruction, nag iba na, naiba na yung boses, naiba na yung words, then malaki po yung bagay na magagawa ng isang guro sa pag iexplain then pagsasabi kung ano po talaga yung dapat gawin” student 5.

“teachers fail to explain the task to be accomplished clearly, completely or comprehensibly”

"..minsan po parang nagbibigay po sila ng instruction tapos pagkatapos po nun, tapos na po so yung students naman po parang magtatanong po sila sa iba na pong students sa mga kaklase po nila tapos hindi na po nila naintindihan tapos iba na po yung ginawa nila kaya po parang minsan po iba na po yung napasa or hindi po yun sa expectation ng teacher... bumababa yung grades ng mga pagsasabi kung ano po talaga yung dapat gawin" student 6.

"..the teacher does not give explanation on what should be done or get student attention during explanation. Students resort to peer inquiry or asking among themselves when explanation is not clear that results to misunderstanding and low expectation or non-conforming outputs"

*".. kasi sila ang nag ge-grade sa amin para maging successful sa performance task. sila ang nagtuturo sa atin kung pano maging successful.."student1. *"..it helps us get more focus on the activity we're doing and sometimes, it supervise us, ..usually they correct our mistakes and the activities we're doing .."*student 2.*

"..the teacher is the one grading the outputs and dictates student success. he or she directs focus to the activity being done and provides correction to mistakes"

The teacher affects the accomplishment of performance task because he/she is the one grading the outputs and dictates student success. The teacher directs students to focus on the activity at hand with supervision and provides correction to mistakes. However, the teacher can also create problems because different subject teachers assign different tasks and levels of difficulty resulting to lost interest, poor motivation and low grades. The teacher can give unclear, incomplete or incomprehensible explanation about the task to be accomplished which results to misunderstanding and low expectation or non-conforming outputs. Teachers dictate student success and they must ensure that learning goals relate to instructional experiences (Airasian, 1994). Goals must be explained through descriptions of engaged activities to improve the accuracy of outputs (Sheppard, 1996).

Students also expressed that the grading system created problems.

".. yung iba po kasi parang wala naman sa rubric tapos parang sabihin nila ngayon na ipapasa

*"..student3,".. kunyari po ano konting pagkakamali lang po, yung ibang teachers po malaki na po yung binabawas po nila.." student 9, *"..minsan po mahirap kasi kelangan po minsan malinis, minsan dapat creative, pero dahil po dito dapat po tayong maging creative po dapat.."*, student 10, *"..ispecify po nila yung rubrics nila po like ano po yung sa tingin nila yung creative, anong gagawin naming para magmumukha syang creative, *"..like ano yung mga bagay na makakapag minus sa grades naming sa rubrics, so siguro ispecify na lang yung mga bagay na yun .."* ..yung ibang teachers mataas yung expectations porket yung mga honor**

students nandun sa isang section , sana pantay pantay po ang tingin nila.." Student 1

"..criteria is not contained in the rubric, unclear, not specific, and grading is subjective.."

"..usually rubrics it helps us determine which subjects we should be more focus on .."student 4.

"..nakakaapekto po ito dahil yung rubrics po dun po nakabatay yung magiging scores po .."student 9,"".. the grading system gives us a warning that ah that we should do better next time .."student 4,"kasi po dun po sa rubric dun po i-iskoran yung tama natin o mali para po sa susunod yung mga mali natin maitama po..."student 11, .."kaya na parang sa susunod, ginagalingan mo.."student3.

"..it affects because the grades are dependent on the rubrics, the grading system tells the areas of improvement, the rubric reflects the score , the errors and the areas of improvement.."

Rubrics or the grading system affects the accomplishment of performance task because it determines which subjects to prioritize. It helps students improve an output through the score. The grading system can become problematic if it contains inaccurate, unclear, undefined and subjective criteria. Rubrics must be well-constructed with identified criteria that differentiates the qualities between a strong or weak performances (Harada and Yoshina 2005).A clear criteria that identifies high achievement levels enable students to attain true levels of mastery (Mehrens, 11998).

There were also identified problems in how the classroom was managed:

".. yung ah, problema kasi pag minsan yung mga kaklase mo na mga mahaharot na mga classmates, pag minsan po ano kung di namamanage po yung classroom parang sa sobrang maharot nila talagang me mga ibang PT po na naapakan, nasisira, so nababawasan yung ano, yung sa cleanliness.. " student2

" students are playful and trample or destroy materials and make the performance task output dirty.

*"..pag maingay po kasi ang klase, di po makapagpokus yung iba po na gumagawa ng PT po dahil nadadamay po sila sa kaingayan po tapos minsan po lumalapit po yung ibang maiingay sa di maiingay para po nagging maingay na din po ang klase.."student 7."..kung magulo po yung classroom, imbes na maayos, yung isa nakakalat dun, yung isa nag cecellphone, nagkukwentuhan dun, yung isa bumibili ng pagkain sa labas .." "student 6, *"....ginagawa nilang excuse yung brainstorming para gumamit ng phone saka imbes na nag uusap sila ng tungkol sa PT, nag uusap lang sila at kung ano -ano pa.."*student2.*

“ student lose focus in a noisy and disorderly class. they treat brainstorming activities as opportunities to become unruly and do irrelevant tasks”

“.. kasi yung sa klase naming ano, mas nauuna yung tropa kesa sa gawain kaya ano ba ang mas pipiliin mo yung mas masaya o yung maistress ka lang ..” student 8, “Nakakaapekto po kapag maingay po at magulo yung classroom at saka po sa mga groups po ano yung mga katamaraan po at iba po magulo so kapag po tamad po yung ka grupo mo or hindi tumutulong, nakakawalang gana na rin pong gumawa ng mga performance task..” student 9, “..kung magulo po yung classroom, imbes na maayos, wala pong makikiisa, wala pong unity..” Student 6, “..naapektuhan po yung magulong klase po kung ano yung PT pag nag i-explain po yung teacher tapos po yung iba pong mga estudyante magugulo, yung mga iba pong nagpopokus at nakikinig naguguluhan po sila at di po nila naiintindihan yung sinasabi ng teacher..” student 11.

“..Isa pa rin dun, yung sa mga PT na kelangan mag kagrupon me mga iba po na sa mga members ng isang group n parang di po tumutulong saka mas lalo pang gumugulo sa ibang grupo ..” student 2, “..nakakaapekto po kapag madumi po at magulo yung classroom, pag maingay po kasi ang klase, di po makapagpokus yung iba po na gumagawa ng PT..” student 7.

“..the students prioritize their friends and enjoyment more than the task simply to enjoy..”..they do not understand the task because of inattentiveness and are uncooperative. . a dirty and disorderly classroom prevents students to maintain focus to the task.”

“.. sobrang laki po ng tulong kapag po maayos po yung classroom kasi po di na po sila madedistract tapos mas pokus na po sila sa mga gawain nila..” Student 13. “..nakakaapekto po yung maayos na klase kasi po yung mga kaklase mo magdadala na po ng mga materials, di na po mang hihingi o kaya manghihiram sa yo tapos wala na pong istorbo..” student 8. “.. pero kapag me unity lahat po makikiisa at gagawa ng kanilang PT hindi yung free time lang at kung ano ano lang yung ginagawa, matatapos po kagad..” student 6 “..para po sakín malaking tulong po yung malinis na classroom pag gumagawa po ng PT kasi po mas gaganahan po kasi po malinis ang paligid..” student 13.”

“..a managed class helps in maintaining focus and prevents distractions. it promotes unity, cooperation, sustains interest and motivation to do the task and ensures the accomplishment the task on time.”

A managed class helps in accomplishing the task because it prevents distraction and sustains focus on the task. It encourages students to bring all the needed materials and prevent borrowing that creates disruptions. It promotes unity, cooperation and ensures that the task is accomplished on time. A clean classroom helps in sustaining interest and motivation to do the task. On the other hand, the problems of an

unmanaged class can lead students to become playful, destructive, and dirty in their outputs. In a noisy class, students are not focused, uncooperative, uneasy, lost, and treat brainstorming activity as free time doing irrelevant activities rather than the task. Accomplishment of a task depends on good classroom management because it ensures good student outcomes (Gage N. 2017) In an unmanaged class, students who are disruptive are academically deficient (Nelson J. 2004) get less instruction (Sutherland, 2008).

Another problem that the student identified was the classroom or venue.

“Nakakaapekto ang isang lugar sa paggawa ng PT kasi minsan masikip, sabay yung iba makikipaglipatan ng upuan, ayun di po magkasya.” Student 15, “.. kapag masikip po yung classroom, di po sila makakagawa ng maayos at saka di sila maka concentrate..” Student 12. “.. pag yung sa classroom magulo, maingay, mahirap i- accomplish pag maraming magulo..” student 14.. “.. kunwari pwede po sa bahay po sya i-shooting, yung iba po hindi pinapayagan..” student 9, “..nagkukulang minsan sa oras, yung iba po naman naghaharot, naglalaro po ..” student 13.

“ ..limited space is not able to accommodate students to rearrange seats if needed and hinders students to perform and concentrate well during activity...venues which are disorderly classroom with noisy students makes the task difficult to accomplish. .. venues outside the school are problematic when parents disallow students to participate, so are time allotment and uncooperative members.. “

Classroom or venue with limited space poses problems in accomplishing performance task because is not able to accommodate students to rearrange seats if needed and hinders students to perform and concentrate well during activity. Disorderly classroom with noisy students makes the task difficult to accomplish. Additionally, venue outside the school creates problems because a student may be prohibited by the parents to join, the allotted time may become insufficient and members become uncooperative.

Lastly, the classroom materials such as equipment and gadgets were sources of problems:

“..minsan po ,tatamarin po yung mga estudyante sa paggawa ng mga example po sa sulat or sa mga PT pag nakita po nila sa tv po..” student 8. “makaka- hinder po ito kung ito po ay kunwari nasa projector po pero di po agad magets ng mga estudyante, di po nila ma pick-up minsan po kelangan po talagang bumalik sa blackboard or manila paper..” Student 6,

“..hindi po lahat tayo ay may wastong kaalaman sa paggamit ng mga ganyan po so yung iba po mas sanay po silang gumamit ng mga libro or mga ganun po..” Student 9.

“Nakakatulong po ito para po mapadali po ang paggawa ng PTs kunwari po sa mga powerpoint po..” student 9. “ Nakakatulong po ito sa aming mga estudyante, pati na din po sa mga teachers, kasi mas mapadali po naming maintindihan kung powerpoint sya..” Student 1. “..pag sa tv

po para po mas makita na po ng lahat, kasi minsan po pag sinusulat po di rin po maintindihan ang sulat ng teacher.. mas makakasave po tayo ng time for the allotted project or allotted discussion para po sa class..” student 5. “

” ..gadgets and equipment make students rely to video presentation and they become lazy to write..” “.. poor manipulative skills hinders student work that they have to resort to book”..”materials help in accomplishing tasks and enhance ability in powerpoint presentation and computer use..” “..they also save time by preventing unreadable handwriting by the teacher and provide current information that allow student interaction..”

Materials such as gadgets and equipment help in making performance tasks easier and enhance ability in presentation and computer use. They benefit both students and teachers by improving classroom and textual presentations and reducing time for the allotted project. However, problems attributed to over reliance in computer or classroom technology encourages laziness while poor manipulative skills delay the accomplishment of a task.

Additional problems identified as the deadline of submission, the emotional or personal state of the student during the task, simultaneous performance tasks, the grouping of students, and the subjectivity of the teacher were acknowledged:

”..Yung emergency po kasi gusto nyo na po umuwi sa hapon, dahil sa personal na gagawin. Student 7,”.. Yun mga one day deadline po i- extend kasi masyadong mabigat nakakastress sana i-extend ng teacher para mas ok sa amin at sa teacher na rin..” student 5, “Minsan po kunwari ah yung teacher ay strict tapos alam na nyang ano, me pipilitin nya pa rin po yung time na ipasa sa isang araw yung mahirap na PT dahil tingin nya po kaya pa rin ng mga estudyante yun kahit mahirap, di nila kayang gawin..” Student 6:

Simultaneous performance tasks, emergencies, valid personal reasons must be considered in giving deadline or extension of deadline. Performance task with one -day time allotment causes emotional stress and is burdensome.

“Yung mga factors po na ito ay maaring yung personal problems ng tao mismo. Kunwari po may PT na mahirap pero halimbawa namatayan yung tao sa bahay nila e di talagang mahihirapan po sya sa paggawa ng PT dahil yun po ang iniisip nya yung tao namatay imbes na yung PT .. tanungin nyo yung tao kung may nangyari ba, ba’t nahihirapan, at bigyan ng consideration, ng chance..” student 6 ,”Sa ngayon po inuuna na po ng iba po yung lovelife nila kesa sa pag aaral so sa groupings po kapag po me PT at mga personal at family problems “. student 9.

Student’s mindset, love-life or family problems, depression, personal problems, bereavement must be given consideration.

“..hindi na po nila itambak po yung bawat PT po kasi po nahihirapan din po yung utak ng bawat estudyante sa isang paaralan po, para po pag paisa- isa lang po bawat subject po maano po yung utak nila hindi po yung na stress lahat po..” student 7, “..kunwari sa isang subject sana isa isang PT lang po wag yung pagsasabay sabayin po nila e di kasi po pagnatatambakan po yung estudyante di na po sila nakakain ng lunch, recess..” student 1,”.. habaan po nila yung schedule ng pagpasa kasi po minsan natatambakan po kami ng ano ng mga PTs, mga tatlo o lima sa isang week.,” student 12”.. medyo dalian and PT saka iwas-iwasan ang pagtatambak ng PT kasi po nahihirapan din po yung mga ibang students, saka nawalan na din po sila ng tingin sa sa sarili nila..” student 10.

Performance tasks should not be given all at the same time because doing so leads to mental stress, insufficient time, pressure, skipped break and meals, low self-confidence

”..bigyan ng teacher ng student na kayang ihandle ng leader, sana yung teacher na un alam naman nya yung capabilities ng students na yun para i-handle ang ibang members ng grupo, kasi kung hindi kaya ng napiling leader mababalewala na yung group work kasi hindi rin gagawa yung iba, hindi rin susunod sa leader nya..” student 5. ” .. kunwari ang naibigay sa iyo yung mga pangit o hindi gumagawa, hindi po pangit.. I mean may matalino sa group na yun, sinasabihan ng iba na kayo na lang ang gumawa, kaya nyo na yan, ayun po ung lider na lang mag-isa tatapos.” student 13.

“..dapat po gawin po nilang individual po yung iba kasi po ano para pag group po ay di po tumutulong lahat so para po pag individual ay matutunan po natin na tumayo sa mga sarili po natin at wag po umasa para sa grades..” student 9.

When grouping students, the teacher should assign members that student leaders can handle according to their capabilities.

“..yung iba po kasing teacher, ano hindi po pantay pantay tingin nila sa mga estudyante, tapos yung iba po nagpopokus lang po sa isa, parang wala na po syang paki sa ibang estudyante yung ganun. Yung suggestion ko lang po sana pantay pantay yung tingin ng mga teachers sa lahat ng estudyante kasi pare- parehas lang po yung mga estudyante na gustong matuto hindi po porket na hindi po sila mabilis matuto papabaya na po nila . Sana mas magbigay po sila attention .” student 1, “Sana sa mga teachers ah go easy on us because we are still learning and growing up and sa mga pagbibigay po ng mga PT sana po ah medyo konting dalian nyo po kasi ah tulad nga po nun we are still growing up..” student 4.

Teachers who are not fair in dealing with students and show no concern should treat students fairly because every student needs to learn. They should give attention to slow learners, be lenient and make every performance task easy for developing students to accomplish.

A Successful Performance Task

This theme describes the characteristics of a successful performance task directly from the minds and experiences of the students.

“..yung parang naleleft ng remarkable impact sa mga students, yung parang nakakatulong sya na maka understand yung mga estudyante sa lesson, saka yung para sa kanya, yung talagang me natutunan talaga ang mga estudyante saka di lang din na parang masaya, saka yung di nakakastress sa mga estudyante..” “ ..I think it helps develop their individual’s creativity and positivity in accomplishing a task or activity provided by the teachers ..” student 4, “..tingin ko po yun yung, pag lahat kayo nag tulong tulong habang gumagawa kyo ng project yung walang inisan ..” student 5, “.. yung ok lang kayo habang gumagawa kayo ng project, yung lahat nagbigay ng effort nila, yung alam nyo para sa inyo na ginawa nyo yung project na yun, na kayo talaga ang gumawa nun,...” student 4, “.. para magkaron kyo ng mataas na grade ma-motivate na gumawa pa ng magagandang PT para sa kanilang mga iba pang subjects..” student 3.

Every student strives for a successful performance task because it reflects the desired objective of the task and leaves a remarkable impact. It helps understand the lesson, reflects learning, and brings joy. Successful performance tasks allow exertion of effort and a good motivation to do quality outputs. They develop creativity, promote cooperation, hard work and positive attitude towards the task through a sense of accomplishment. If problems in accomplishing the task can be minimized then development of real- world skills is easily attainable (Utman, 1997).

IV. CONCLUSION

The study intended to find out the problems that grade 8 students encounter in accomplishing performance tasks in relation to the teacher, assessment, classroom management, learning environment, classroom technology and others. It also sought to establish the predictors of a successful performance task relative to the identified variables. The findings had confirmed that there exist specific problems pertaining to the teacher, assessment, learning environment or venue, classroom management, and classroom materials. Furthermore, the deadline of submission, students’ emotional and personal state, simultaneous performance tasks, teacher’s subjectivity and grouping of students are contributory to unaccomplished performance tasks. Among these problems, the learning environment or venue is the greatest predictor followed by classroom management, assessment, classroom materials and teacher.

From the findings, the study has the following implications. First, appropriate measures must be undertaken to address the problems that are attributable to the teacher, assessment, learning environment or venue, classroom management, classroom materials, deadline of submission, students’ emotional and personal state, simultaneous performance tasks, teacher’s subjectivity and grouping of students in future performance tasks. Second, any initiative of improvement must prioritize the aspect of learning

environment or venue followed by classroom management, assessment, classroom materials and teachers. Lastly, the study can contribute in education and research as a source of data for future similar researches.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We would like to express our gratitude for the training and financial support extended to the researchers Letran Research Center, Colegio de San Juan de Letran-Manila.

REFERENCES

- [1] Abbott, A. L., & Wren, D. G. (2016). Using Performance Task Data to Improve Instruction. Clearing House Airasian, P. W. (2000). Assessment in the classroom a concise approach. Boston: McGraw-Hill.
- [2] Andrade, Heidi G. n.d. Understanding Rubrics. Cambridge, MA: Harvard Graduate School of Education and Project Zero. 10 March 2006 (<http://learnweb.harvard.edu/ALPS/thinking/docs/rubricar.htm>).
- [3] Airasian, P. W. (2001). Classroom assessment: Concepts and application. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- [4] Anderson, R. S. (1998). Why talk about different ways to grade? The shift from traditional assessment to alternative assessment. *New Directions for Teaching and Learning*, 74,5-16. doi: 10.1002/tl.7401
- [5] Aycock, A., Gamham, C. & Kaleta, R. (2002, March 20). Lessons teamed from the hybrid course project [Electronic version]. *Teaching with Technology Today*. 8(6). Retrieved September 2, 2008, from <http://www.uwsa.edu/ttt/articles/gamham2.htm>
- [6] Bintz, W. P. (1991). Staying connected: Exploring new functions for assessment. *Contemporary Education*, 62(4),
- [7] Bransford, J. D. (1979). Human cognition: Learning, understanding, and remembering. Belmont, CA: Wadsworth.
- [8] Bullens, D. (2002). Authentic assessment: Change for the future (Master’s Thesis). Available from ERIC database. (ERIC No. ED468067)
- [9] Castillo-Montoya, M. (2016). Preparing for Interview Research: The Interview Protocol Refinement Framework. *The QualitativeReport*, 21(5), 811-831.
- [10] Chun, M. (2012). Performance Tasks and the Pedagogy of Broadway.
- [11] Creswell, J. W. (2007). *Qualitative inquiry & research design: Choosing among five traditions* (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- [12] Cubin, L., Kirkpatrick, H., & Peck, C. (2001). “High Access and Low Use of Technologies in High School Classrooms: Explaining an Apparent Paradox.” *American Educational Research Journal*, 38(4), 813-834.
- [13] Dwyer, C. A. (1998). Assessment and classroom learning: Theory and practice. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 5(1), 131-137. doi:10.1080/0969595980050109
- [14] Assessment Is Instruction and Instruction Is Assessment: Using Rubrics to Promote Thinking and Understanding.”
- [15] Gaverly, D. C, Nicholson, S. A., & Radcliffe, R. (2004). The effectiveness of strategic reading instruction for college developmental readers. *The Journal of College Reading & Learning*. 35{ 1 }, 25 - 49.
- [16] Harada, V.H. and Joan M. Yoshina.2004. *Inquiry Learning Through Librarian- Teacher Partnerships*. Worthington, OH: Linworth.
- [17] Hetland, L. & Veenema, S. eds. *The Project Zero Classroom: Views on Understanding*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard Graduate School of Education. 10 March 2006 (www.lookstein.org/heterogeneous/hetero_edu_rubrics.htm).
- [18] Kaplan, A., Middleton, M. J., Urdan, T., & Midgley, C. (2002). Achievement goals and goal structures. In C. Midgley (Ed.), *Goals, structures and patterns of adaptive learning* (pp. 21-53). Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum.
- [19] Kim, S. (2005). Effects of implementing performance assessment on student learning: Meta-analysis using Hlm (Un- published doctoral dissertation). The Pennsylvania State University, ProQuest Information and Learning Company.
- [20] Kubiszyn, T., & Borich, G. (1993). *Educational testing and measurement: Classroom application and practice* (4th ed.). New York: Harper Collins College.

- [21] Kurthen, il., & Smith, G. G. (2005/2006). Hybrid online face-to-face teaching: When is it an efficient learning tool? *International Journal of Learning* 12(5) 237-245.
- [22] Lengel, J.G., & Lengel, K.M. (2006). *Integrating Technology: A Practical Guide*. Boston, MA: Pearson Education.
- [23] Lewis, G. (2009). *Bringing Technology into the Classroom*. Great Clarendon Street: Oxford University Press.
- [24] Linn, R. L., & Gronlund, N. E. (2000). *Measurement and assessment in teaching*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Merrill.
- [25] Logan, C. R. (1996). *The relationship between instruction and assessment (Unpublished doctoral dissertation)*. The Pennsylvania State University, ProQuest Information and Learning Company.
- [26] Maffett, S. P. (2007). Education at a distance: Community colleges implement distance learning to reach developmental learners. *Community College Journal*, 34-39.
- [27] Mehrens, W. A. (1992). Using performance assessment for accountability purposes. *Educational Measurement: Issues and Practice*, 11(1), 3-9.
- [28] Metin, M. (2011). The examinations of teachers' attitude towards performance assessment with respect to the different variables. *Energy Education Science and Technology Part B: Social and Educational Studies*, 3(3), 269-284.
- [29] Metin, M. (2012). Investigation of primary students' opinions about using performance assessment in science and technology course with respect to the different variables. *Asia-Pacific Forum on Science Learning and Teaching*, 13(2), 135-159
- [30] Nash, R. D. (2005). Course completion rates among distance learners: Identifying possible methods to improve retention. *Online Journal of Distance Learning Administration*, 8(4). Retrieved August 15, 2008, from <http://www.westga.edu/~distance/ojdla/>
- [31] Nitko, A. J. (2004). *Educational assessment of students (4th ed.)*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- [32] Parris, S.R., Fisher, D., & Headley, K. (2009). *Adolescent Literacy Field Tested: Effective Solutions for Every Classroom*. Newark, DE: International Reading Association, Inc. Pedretti,
- [33] Pavia, C. M. (2004). Issues of attitude and access: A case study of basic writers in a computer classroom. *Journal of Basic Writing*, 23(2) 4-22.
- [34] Prensky, M. (2001, September/October). Digital natives, digital immigrants. *On the Horizon*. (5), 1-6.
- [35] Roche, A., Clarke, D., Sullivan, P., & Cheeseman, J. (2013). Strategies for Encouraging Students to Persist in challenging tasks: Some insights from work in classrooms. *Australian Primary Mathematics Classroom*
- [36] Schendel, R., & Tolmie, A. (2017). Beyond translation: adapting a performance-task-based assessment of critical thinking ability for use in Rwanda. *Assessment & Evaluation In Higher Education*
- [37] Shalev, N., Humphreys, G., & Demyere, N. (2018). Manipulating perceptual parameters in a continuous performance task. *Behavior Research Methods*
- [38] Spady, W., & Marshall, K. (1991). Beyond traditional outcomes-based education. *Educational Leadership*, 49, 67-72.
- [39] Stine, L. (2004). The best of both worlds: Teaching basic writers in class and online. *Journal of Basic Writing* 23(2), 49-69.
- [40] Tinto, V. (2008, June 9). Access without support is not opportunity [Electronic version]. *Inside Higher Ed*. Retrieved August 9, 2008, from <http://insidehighered.com/views/2008/06/09/tinto>
- [41] Utman, C. H. (1997). Performance effects of motivational state: A meta-analysis. *Personality and Social Psychology Review*, 1, 170-182.
- [42] Wartella, E.A., & Jennings, N. (2000, Fall/Winter). "Children and Computers: New Technology Old Concerns." *The Future of Children: Children and Computer Technology*, 10,
- [43] Welker, J., & Berardino, L. (2005-2006). Blended learning: Understanding the middle ground between traditional classroom and fully online instruction. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*. 34(1), 33
- [44] Williams, B. T. (2009). *Shimmering Literacies: Popular Culture & Reading & Writing Online*. New York, NY: Peter Lang.
- [45] Yena, L., & Waggoner, Z. (2003). One size fits all?: Student perspectives on face-to-face and online writing pedagogies [Electronic version]. *Computers & Composition Online*. Retrieved October 17, 2008, from <http://www.bgsu.edu/~cconline/yena-waggoner/index.html>
- [46] Young, A., & Norgard, C. (2006). Assessing the quality of online courses from the students' perspective. *Internet & Higher Education*. 9(2). 107-115.